

Frequency Dependence of Dielectric Properties of $\text{Cu}_{0.7+x}\text{Cd}_{0.3}\text{Zr}_x\text{Fe}_{2-2x}\text{O}_4$ Spinel System

Ganesh B. Akat*¹, Balwan U. Patil*²

**Department of Chemistry, Kohinoor Arts, Commerce & Science College, Khultabad.
Dist. Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar. (MS) India – 431101*

***Department of Physics, Kohinoor Arts, Commerce & Science College, Khultabad.
Dist. Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar. (MS) India - 431101*

Abstract - This study investigates the frequency dependence of dielectric properties in the $\text{Cu}_{0.7+x}\text{Cd}_{0.3}\text{Zr}_x\text{Fe}_{2-2x}\text{O}_4$ spinel system, focusing on the influence of varying Zr content (x) on the dielectric behavior. Spinel ferrites are well-known for their versatile applications in electronics, particularly in high-frequency devices, due to their unique electrical and magnetic properties. The materials were synthesized using a conventional solid-state reaction method. X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis confirmed the formation of single-phase spinel structures with a slight shift in lattice parameters due to the incorporation of Zr ions. Dielectric measurements were carried out over a broad frequency range from 1 KHz to 10 KHz. The results revealed that the dielectric constant (ϵ') decreases with increasing frequency, which is typical of ferrite materials and can be attributed to the Maxwell-Wagner interfacial polarization. Additionally, the dielectric loss ($\tan \delta$) exhibited a similar frequency-dependent behavior, initially decreasing and then stabilizing at higher frequencies. The variation of Zr content within the spinel lattice significantly influenced the dielectric properties, with an optimal composition observed around $x = 0.1$. This variation is attributed to the modification of $\text{Fe}^{3+}/\text{Fe}^{2+}$ ion distribution between octahedral and tetrahedral sites, altering the polarization mechanism. The study demonstrates that tailoring the Zr content in the Cu-Cd ferrite matrix allows fine-tuning of the dielectric properties, making these materials suitable for specific applications in electronics, such as capacitors and inductors, where frequency-dependent behavior is crucial.

Keywords: *Spinel ferrite, dielectric properties, frequency dependence, Zr doping, Maxwell-Wagner polarization, etc.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Ferrites have a wide Spread role in many technological Applications due to their magnetic properties, high electrical Resistivity, low eddy currents and dialectic loss. Ferrites are extensively used in microwave device, computers, memory Chips, magnetic recording media etc. It is well Known that when ferrites are sufficiently diluted with non-magnetic atoms, they can show a wide Spectrum of magnetic structure, ferromagnetic Order, cluster spin Glass etc. [1]

Copper ferrite and copper containing ferrites have been Focus of continuous interest in the recent years. The spinel Ferrites containing varying amount of zinc form a class of important material. It has been reported that the addition of tetravalent ions like Ti^{4+} , Ge^{4+} and Sn^{4+} in Copper ferrite influences structural and magnetic properties of the system. [2]

Several Studies have been reported on the addition Zr^{2+} ions in copper, magnesium and other ferrites [3-8]. However, no reports have been found in the literature regarding structural, cation distribution, electrical and magnetic properties of $\text{Cu}_{0.7+x}\text{Cd}_{0.3}\text{Zr}_x\text{Fe}_{2-2x}\text{O}_4$ ($x = 0.0$ to 0.5) mixed ferrites.

The aim of this chapter is to present the results of investigation of structural, cation distribution, electrical and magnetic properties of $\text{Cu}_{0.7+x}\text{Cd}_{0.3}\text{Zr}_x\text{Fe}_{2-2x}\text{O}_4$ ($x = 0.0$ to 0.5) spinels by means of X-ray diffraction, IR, D.C. resistivity, dielectric measurements, magnetization and a.c. susceptibility measurements systematically.

II. EXPERIMENTAL & SAMPLE PREPARATION

Ferrite sample having compositional formula $\text{Cu}_{0.7+x}\text{Cd}_{0.3}\text{Zr}_x\text{Fe}_{2-2x}\text{O}_4$ ($x = 0.0$ to 0.5) were prepared by conventional ceramic technique. The analytical grade reagent of Fe_2O_3 , CuO , CdO_2 and ZrO_2 (all 99.9% pure, supplied by E. Merck) were mixed in proper Proportions and were finely ground. The finely ground powder was sintered at 700°C for 12 hours and then slowly cooled to room temperature at a rate of $2^\circ\text{C}/\text{minute}$. The sintered powder was reground and sieved through a mesh (100 BSS) and pellets of 1cm diameter were prepared under a pressure of 5 tones/inch². Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) was mixed as a binder during the preparation of pellets. The

pellets were finally sintered at 980⁰c for 24 hours and slowly cooled to room temperature at the rate of 2⁰ c/minute using muffle furnace with controller.

III. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Frequency dependence of the dielectric behavior of simple and mixed ferrites has been reported by many Workers [9-12]. The dispersion in the dielectric properties of the polycrystalline ferrites has been attributed to the inhomogeneous nature of these materials as suggested by Maxwell [12] and Wanger [13]. Phenomenological theory for polycrystalline ferrites has been suggested by Koops [10]. C. Parkash et al [14] have reported dielectric behavior of tetravalent titanium substituted Ni-Zn ferrites. They have attributed the dielectric Constant ϵ' to the interfacial polarization.

Figure.1 [a, b, c] show variation of dielectric constant (ϵ'), dielectric loss (ϵ'') and loss tangent ($\tan \delta$) with the frequency. The compositional variation of dielectric constant (ϵ'), dielectric loss (ϵ'') and loss tangent ($\tan \delta$) are listed in Table 1. It is evident from Figure .1a and Table 1 that,

- 1) The dielectric constant (ϵ'), dielectric loss (ϵ'') and loss tangent ($\tan \delta$) initially increase with increase in Zr^{2+} Content and after some value of Zr^{2+} concentration it decrease.
- 2) As frequency increase ϵ' decreases from a large value to low value and remains constant in high frequency range.

This abnormal behavior of Zr substituted Cu-Cd ferrite has been observed in copper containing ferrite by other workers [15]. The abnormal behavior is attributed to the existence of Cu^{2+} ions in the ferrites; while polarization process is attributed to verse conduction mechanism. Hence, the dielectric behavior with frequency of the present system is ruled out.

In the present system, ϵ' decreases rapidly with increase in frequency and reaches a constant value. Similar behavior was observed in different ferrite [16]. The observed variation in the dielectric relaxation intensity can be explained on the basis of space charge polarization due to inhomogeneous dielectric structure as discussed by Maxwell [12] and Wagner [13].

Table I
Compositional variation of dielectric constant (ϵ'), Dielectric Loss (ϵ'') and $\tan \delta$ at 10 KHz and 1 MHz for $Cu_{0.7+x}Cd_{0.3}Zr_xFe_{2-2x}O_4$ system

Composition x	Dielectric Measurements at 10 KHz frequency			Dielectric measurements at 1 MHz frequency		
	ϵ'	ϵ''	$\tan \delta$	ϵ'	ϵ''	$\tan \delta$
0.1	62.07	117.63	1.89	41.44	5.01	0.12
0.2	73.34	31.02	0.42	49.35	3.553	0.07
0.3	70.78	23.85	0.33	50.08	2.929	0.05
0.4	98.81	52.57	0.53	64.29	4.43	0.06
0.5	55.05	21.40	0.39	37.39	2.76	0.07

Fig. 1 a) Variation of Dielectric Constant (ϵ') with frequency for $\text{Cu}_{0.7+x}\text{Cd}_{0.3}\text{Zr}_x\text{Fe}_{2-2x}\text{O}_4$ system

Fig. 1 b) Variation of Dielectric loss (ϵ'') with frequency for $\text{Cu}_{0.7+x}\text{Cd}_{0.3}\text{Zr}_x\text{Fe}_{2-2x}\text{O}_4$ system

Fig. 1 c) Variation of dielectric loss tangent ($\tan\delta$) with Frequency for $\text{Cu}_{0.7+x}\text{Cd}_{0.3}\text{Zr}_x\text{Fe}_{2-2x}\text{O}_4$ system

IV. CONCLUSION

From the above experimental results, it may be concluded that the frequency dependence of dielectric constant (ϵ'), dielectric loss (ϵ'') and dielectric loss tangent ($\tan\delta$) decreases with increase in frequency and remains constant at high frequency range.

REFERENCES

- [1] J.L. Dormann and M. Nogues, *J. Phys. Condensed Matter* 2 (1990) 1223
- [2] B.L. Patil, S.R. Sawant, and S.A. Patil, *Czechoslovak Journal of Physics* 43 (1993) 87
- [3] D.S. Birajdar, U.N. Devatwal and K.M. Jadhav, *J. Mat. Sci.* (Communicated)
- [4] S.R. Sawant and S.S. Suryawanshi, *Current Science* 57 (1988) 12
- [5] S.S. Suryawanshi, S.R. Jadhav, S.A. Patil and S.R. Sawant *Mat Res. Bull.* 24 (1990) 1201
- [6] S.R. Sawant and R.N. Patil, *Bull. Mat. Sci.* 4 (1982) 11
- [7] S.R. Sawant, D.S. Birajdar, S.S. Suryawanshi, A.M. Sankpal, B.L. Patil, S.A. Patil and R.N. Patil *Ind. J. pure and Appl. Physics* 28 (1990) 424
- [8] R.G. KulKarni and V.U. Patil, *J. of Mat. Sci.* 17 (1982) 843
- [9] N. Rezlescu and F. Rezlescu *Physics Status Solidi A* 23 (1974) 575
- [10] C. G. Koops- *Phys. Rev.* 83 (1951) 121
- [11] Z. Molten *Angew. Phys.* 4 (1952) 216
- [12] J. C. Maxwell "Electricity and Magnetism" Oxford Univ-Press London 1 (1873)
- [13] K.W. Wanger- *Ann. Physica* 40 (1913) 828
- [14] C. Prakash and J. S. Bajjal *J. of Less Common Metals* 51 (1985) 107
- [15] N. Rezlescu and E. Rezlescu *Physics Status Solidi A* 59 (1980) 323
- [16] L. Neel *Proc. Phys. SocA* 65 (1952) 869